

A quantum propulsion method

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ABSTRACT: Experimental proof of concept for a new propulsion method is presented. Ammonia gas (NH_3) is exposed to a strong electric field aiming to align the orientation of the polar molecules. This results in partial alignment of the quantum tunneling of nitrogen atoms, specific for the ammonia, creating bias in the pressure distribution and a resultant force. Two experimental examples demonstrate that a sealed container filled with ammonia can be accelerated after exposing the gas to the electric field. The new method has the advantages to be applicable in any medium and to be environmentally safe.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a new approach to propulsion, involving the quantum tunneling phenomenon. Technologies based on quantum tunneling have been long present on the market. Well-known examples include:

- The first atomic clock built in 1949 at the U.S. National Bureau of Standards. Quantum tunneling oscillations were utilized to correct irregularities in the crystal-controlled oscillator (Lyons 1957).
- The maser built in 1953 at Columbia University was a predecessor of lasers (Gordon et al. 1955). The maser utilizes stimulated emission of ammonia molecules to produce amplification of microwaves at a frequency related to the quantum tunneling of nitrogen.
- The tunnel diodes invented in 1957 at Tokyo Tsushin Kogyo (Esaki 1958) were utilizing the electron tunneling effect.

Recent major investments in quantum computing, communications and sensing include:

- European Quantum Flagship (Oct 2018)
- US National Quantum Initiative Act (Dec 2018)

The question is can quantum tunneling be also used for power & propulsion? Similar to the masers and the atomic clocks, the proposed in this paper propulsion method relies on the unique quantum properties of the anhydrous ammonia.

What would be the benefits of this approach? The quantum propulsion method is expected to produce:

- A universal for any medium drive that can work in water, air, and vacuum.
- An environmentally safe combustionless drive that does not interact chemically with the environment.
- Easy to maintain drive with no moving parts.

Propulsion methods, which do not rely for thrust on the surrounding medium are being sought because of the many benefits they may bring (White et al. 2017, Georgevic 1973, Bae 2008). Such methods can be universal for any medium, allowing the utilization of a single vehicle for ground, air, water and space applications. These methods may also enable manned deep-space travel for destinations where the conventional jet propulsion drives would run out of propellant before reaching the required speeds for practical trip durations.

The objective of the quantum propulsion is similar to the methods listed above, but the mechanism is very different. The underlying theory was not even developed with propulsion in mind; the new method rather emerged as a by-product demo. The testing started with the objective to trigger a very large number of quantum tunneling events in ionic crystals. Several years later, the problem was simplified not to attempt triggering tunneling events, but to utilize well-known existing tunneling cases, such as the quantum tunneling of nitrogen in the ammonia molecule.

The presented here experiments represent a proof of concept that is already showing a ten times higher thrust-to-power ratio than a recently tested competing concept (White et al. 2017). The thrust-to-power ratio is expected to increase after applying the proposed in this paper optimization strategy.

The focus of the manuscript is on the experimental findings. The next section presents the portion of the theory that is directly related to the experiments.

2 THEORY

Ammonia is a colorless gas with a characteristic smell (Yost 2007). The ammonia molecules (NH_3) have a pyramidal shape. Ammonia was selected for this study because of its nitrogen inversion - a known process (Feynman 1965) where the nitrogen jumps back and forth through the plane formed by the three hydrogen atoms. The nitrogen shifts occur billions of times per second for each molecule at room temperature. The inversion is a quantum tunneling process, because the nitrogen should not be able to cross in a classical sense the energy barrier created by the three hydrogen atoms. Note that the quantum tunneling speed is in the order of the speed of light (Eckle 2008), which is much higher than the molecular velocities due to thermal motions. Therefore, the ammonia molecule resembles a little piston operating at nearly infinite speeds in the GHz frequency range; see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Nitrogen inversion.

The presented method aims to organize a large number of molecules ($\sim 10^{20}$) to work together, so their microwork can benefit the macro scale. Even if it is impossible to employ all the ammonia molecules in a given volume, we could at least try using a sufficiently large portion of them.

The nitrogen atom has atomic number 7 in comparison to the hydrogen's 1. The ammonia molecules are polar, and the quantum tunneling of the relatively heavy nitrogen atom is expected to affect the molecular collisions of ammonia the way a discontinuous, almost instant process would affect the laws of motion. The tunneling is expected to affect the collisions in a random way before applying the high voltage to the gas. Because of the molecule polarity, the strong electric field tries to orient the molecular dipoles, inducing some directionality bias in the orien-

tation of the molecules during the collisions. This makes the pressure distribution less random and creates a resultant force on the container walls.

The work cycles of each molecular “piston” consist of:

Figure 2. Work cycle.

An oriented “piston” may contribute to the global resultant force during collisions with other molecules.

Two questions were raised regarding the described above mechanism:

1. Would the electric field be able to orient the molecular dipoles billions of times per second?
2. Wouldn't the electric field interfere with, or even stop the quantum tunneling?

The answer to the first question is: depends. It would be possible because even nanoparticles can be rotated with a laser at GHz rates (Ahn 2018), and the ammonia molecule is much lighter than a nanoparticle. In some cases, however, the quick orientation may be impossible, because the thermal motion may include an angular momentum component too high for the field to overcome in the very short time between two consecutive molecular collisions. Thus, the new propulsion method relies on the molecules with a sufficiently low angular momentum that the field can handle. As a part of the future optimization, we will try stopping the thermal rotational motion of the molecules with a laser (Lien 2014) before orienting them with the field. This should increase the number of employed (oriented) molecules.

The answer to the second question is also: depends. Note that the applied electric field pulses in a single direction. Even if the peaks of the field are sufficiently high to stop the tunneling in a single direction, or in both directions, there would be a point of time between the zero and the maximum field strength where the tunneling can still occur.

The presented experiments in the next section demonstrate that a sealed container with ammonia can be accelerated without a global external reaction. The underlying hypothesis is that the reaction would be partially taken by the quantum tunneling of the relatively heavy nitrogen atoms. It is presumed that when a neighboring molecule pushes on the nitrogen

atom, it would not fully transfer the momentum to the three hydrogen atoms, because if it did comply with the classic conservation law, the hydrogen atoms would have not allowed the nitrogen to cross in-between. The experiments were designed to prove this effect.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Experimental setup

Figures 4 and 5 show two experimental examples of quantum propulsion. In the experiments, a sealed container (shown as a blue oval) is filled with ammonia gas. The container has two electrodes penetrating the walls without compromising the seal. The electrodes are situated sufficiently far from each other to prevent arc discharge when exposed to the design high voltage. The electronics outside of the oval container consists of a 6V heavy-duty battery, 400 kV Tesla-coil type DC pulse generator, and a wireless control box. The setup allows turning the pulse generator on and off remotely. The electronics and the ammonia container are placed inside a larger sealed container, shown with a double-red line. There is a third, even larger transparent container used to shield the moving test container from any unintended external airflows.

The parameters of the moving container, including contents, are given in Table 1. The oval container is filled with evaporated from 10% solution ammonia gas at atmospheric pressure.

The setup was always left overnight to reach equi-

librium, so the voltage can be applied after the container stopped moving. The magnetic field was measured outside the moving container while turning the electric field on and off to ensure the setup doesn't produce spikes, which may interact with Earth's magnetic field, and create some uncertainties when evaluating the driving mechanism (Figure 3).

Table 1. Parameters of the accelerating container

Parameter	Value
Mass	1.146 kg
Dimensions* (length x width x height)	24 x 16 x 12 cm
Distance between the electrodes	6 cm
NH ₃ volume (at atmospheric pressure)	~5 cm ³
Input voltage	6 V
Input current	0.53 A

* The dimensions of the shielding box were 58 x 38 x 30 cm

Note the following safety precautions:

- *Electric arcs may ignite anhydrous ammonia at certain concentrations. Therefore, to avoid a fire hazard, the test container is filled with ammonia after evacuating the air.*
- *Anhydrous ammonia can be highly corrosive, so the materials, such as polyethylene, stainless steel and aluminum, are selected to be chemically resistant to this gas.*
- *Anhydrous ammonia is toxic and should be handled according to the established safety regulations.*

Figure 3. Initial magnetic field check

3.2 Experimental results

After applying voltage, the sealed container moves in a translational way if the electrodes are placed along the centerline (Figure 4), or in a rotational way if the electrodes are placed along the tangent (Figure 5). Figure 6 shows the rotational motion of the setup corresponding to Figure 5. The translational motion corresponding to Figure 4 was not precisely measured, but it was slower due to the drag and added

mass from the water. The motions were video recorded.

Based on the measured motion, the new propulsion method produces approximately 10 $\mu\text{N/W}$ efficiency, which is ten times higher than another recently tested concept (White et al. 2017). Note that this is an un-optimized setup with just a few cubic centimeters of ammonia gas at atmospheric pressure.

3.3 Optimization strategy

In the future work, the setup will be optimized for higher efficiency by varying the size of the container, the area and the number of the electrodes, the high-voltage and the pressure of the ammonia. Furthermore, the efficiency should depend on the ability of the electric field to orient the molecular dipoles. A significant portion of the molecules, however, may have angular momentums that cannot be stopped by the electric field between two consecutive collisions with their neighbors.

Figure 4. An experimental example of translational motion

Figure 5. An experimental example of rotational motion

The utilized pulsing DC field is not the most efficient method to orient molecular dipoles. Therefore, future optimization also envisions the utilization of lasers to stop the molecular rotors (Lien 2014) before applying the electric field to orient the molecules. There have been significant developments in the quantum control of molecular rotation during the recent years, as listed in the following overview (Koch et al. 2018). Several methods use a combination of a moderate electrostatic field and an intense nonresonant rapidly turned-off laser field (Goban et al. 2008, Nielsen et al. 2012, Omiste J., and González-Férez 2016). Zhdanov & Zadkov 2008 showed that molecular orientation can be generated by a three-color laser field at room temperature. Terahertz-laser-induced two-level coherence and field-free orientation with application to ammonia molecules was simulated by Owens et al. 2017. This line of research has not been intended for developing new propulsion techniques, but has been directed towards controlled chemistry and controlled quantum state applications. Nevertheless, cooperation with laboratories developing theoretical and experimental techniques for orienting a large number of gaseous molecules may benefit the development of a more efficient quantum drive.

The proposed optimization should reveal to what extent the thrust efficiency depends on the applied power. The propulsion may be due to a compound

Figure 6. Measured rotational motion

effect of thermal motions, quantum tunneling motions and the ratio between oriented and non-oriented ammonia molecules, but only the last parameter depends on the electrical input power.

4 DISCUSSION

The experiments show that a sealed container at a static equilibrium can be moved with a remote control, but how certain is it that the measured motion is

due to quantum effects? The following discussion eliminates several possible competing explanations.

The motion is not due to mechanical interactions for the following reasons:

- ✓ There are no gas leaks because the ammonia is inside two sealed containers.
- ✓ All electronic components and batteries are also located inside the sealed moving container.
- ✓ There are no mechanical vibrations, which would have been obvious from the ripples they would have created in the water.
- ✓ Rotational motion of the gas may cause rotation of the container (in the opposite direction) due to the conservation of the angular momentum, but it cannot explain the translational motion achieved in the other set of experiments.
- ✓ There are no voltage arcs, and no increase in temperature of the containers, which could have generated air currents outside. Any increase in the gas temperature would have caused a visible volume increase of the inner soft container.
- ✓ External air-currents are shielded with the outer transparent box.

The motion is not due to electromagnetic interactions for the following reasons:

- ✓ Magnetic interaction with the environment outside the container would have resulted in oscillations around Earth's magnetic North direction, or around the direction of the nearest external magnet. The container would have stopped eventually like a compass needle aligning with the magnetic North. It would have not produced the continuous rotation that was measured.
- ✓ The magnetic field near the moving container was also checked with a magnetometer and with a compass, which did not show any visible spikes when applying voltage.
- ✓ Any electromagnetic waves generated during the experiments would have not had the power to move a 1kg container.

This line of reasoning leads to the conclusion that, as expected, the reaction is being taken locally by the quantum tunneling of the nitrogen atoms. The lack of global reaction makes this method useful in a very unique way.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The presented experimental proof-of-concept is significant because it demonstrates how quantum tunneling processes at a micro scale can contribute to macro-scale motions, opening opportunities for medium-independent propulsion. Currently, different vehicles use different reaction depending on their operating environment. The quantum propulsion, however, can be universal - a ground vehicle could

be used in air, underwater or in the outer space, without expelling mass or polluting the environment.

The demonstrated efficiency of the method is still low except possibly for space applications. An optimization strategy focusing on existing laser techniques for molecular orientation is outlined.

The next study will focus on optimizing the efficiency of the new method.

REFERENCES

- Ahn, J., Xu, Z., Bang, J., Deng, Y.-H., Hoang, T. M., Han, Q., Ma, R.-M., and Li, T. 2018. Optically Levitated Nanodumbbell Torsion Balance and GHz Nanomechanical Rotor, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 121, 033603.
- Bae, Y. K. 2008. Photonic Laser Propulsion: Proof-of-Concept Demonstration. *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets.* 45 (1: 153–155.
- Eckle, P., Pfeiffer, A. N., Cirelli, C., Staudte, A., Dorner, R., Muller, H. G., Buttiker, M., Keller, U. 2008. Attosecond Ionization and Tunneling Delay Time Measurements in Helium, *Science* 322 (5907): 1525–1529.
- Esaki, L. 1958. "New Phenomenon in Narrow Germanium p-n Junctions". *Physical Review.* 109 (2): 603–604.
- Feynman, R. P., Robert L., Sands, M. 1965. The Hamiltonian matrix. *The Feynman Lectures on Physics. Vol. 3*, Addison-Wesley, Massachusetts, USA.
- Georgevic, R. M. 1973. The Solar Radiation Pressure Forces and Torques Model, *The Journal of the Astronautical Sciences, Vol. 27, No. 1, Jan–Feb.*
- Goban, A., Minemoto S., and Sakai H. 2008, Laser-Field-Free Molecular Orientation, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 101, 013001
- Gordon, J. P., Zeiger, H. J., Townes, C. H. 1955. The Maser—New Type of Microwave Amplifier, Frequency Standard, and Spectrometer. *Phys. Rev.* 99 (4): 1264.
- Koch, C. P., Lemesko, M. and Sugny, D. 2018. Quantum control of molecular rotation. *arXiv:1810.11338v1 [quant-ph]*
- Lien, C.-Y., Seck, C. M., Lin, Y.-W., Nguyen, J. H. V., Tabor D. A., and Odom, B. C. 2014. Broadband optical cooling of molecular rotors from room temperature to the ground state, *Nature Communications* 5, Article number: 4783.
- Lyons, H. 1957. Atomic Clocks, *Scientific American, Inc*
- Nielsen, J., Stapelfeldt, H., Küpper, J., Friedrich, B., Omiste, J. and Gonzalez-Ferez, R. 2012. Making the Best of Mixed-Field Orientation of Polar Molecules: A Recipe for Achieving Adiabatic Dynamics in an Electrostatic Field Combined with Laser Pulses. *Physical Review Letters.* 108. 193001. 10.1103/PhysRevLett.108.193001.
- Omiste J., and González-Férez R. 2016. Theoretical description of the mixed-field orientation of asymmetric-top molecules: A time-dependent study, *Phys. Rev. A* 94, 063408 – Published 9 December
- Owens, A., Zak, E. J., Chubb, K., Yurchenko, S., N., Tennyson, J. and Yachmenev, A. 2017, *Scientific Reports volume 7, Article number: 45068*
- White, H., March, P., Lawrence, J., Jerry Vera, Sylvester, A., Brady, D., and Bailey, P. 2017. Measurement of Impulsive

Thrust from a Closed Radio-Frequency Cavity in Vacuum,
Journal of Propulsion and Power, Vol. 33, No. 4, pp. 830-841.

Yost, D. M.. 2007, Ammonia and Liquid Ammonia Solutions.
Systematic Inorganic Chemistry. READ BOOKS. p. 132.

Zhdanov D. V. and Zadkov, D. V. 2008, Laser-assisted orientation-dependent selection of molecules as a tool of symmetry breaking in isotropic molecular ensembles, *Phys. Rev. A* 77, 011401.